

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING THE NATIVE LANGUAGE IN THE FORMATION OF SPEECH OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: this article will talk about the importance of learning the native language in shaping the speech of Primary School students, ways of growing speech, and the shortcomings found in the speech of students

Keywords: primary education, speech, vocabulary, native language, colloquial and linguistic competencies, method, teacher, pupil

Today, Education of young people with high morale , national and Universal views, followers of our future using modern, advanced pedagogical technologies, while at the same time requiring representatives of primary education to responsibly approach their field in helping them to deeply understand the goals and objectives of the educational system based on the demand of the time. .Teachers of the primary class should develop their speech in the process of extracting the literacy of students, as well as in the process of extracting the literacy of students.The main goal of teaching the native language in schools is also to develop the speech of students , to form the skills of being able to speak correctly , fluently in them .The process of growing speech in elementary grades is important not only in native language classes , but also in Alphabet classes. The main foundation in the cultivation of speech in a child is laid in the lessons of the alphabet in the 1st grade. In this case , the child must clearly pronounce the sounds he is learning, be able to combine syllables and express the expression of words in writing in speech. Speech cultivation itself what is it? If the work of the reader and his work through the language is envisaged , then speech cultivation is understood as an active practical transformation of the student's work performed in every possible way (pronunciation , vocabulary, syntactic

construction, linkage speech). Speech cultivation in students is carried out in the main three directions. These are working on the word

- work on vocabulary and sentence;
- work on linked speech

.Work on the route or national get-through . all of the work in the above three baskets teaching in the lessons of the native language, including the teaching of the baskets are organized in connection with the cultivation of speech and thinking of students in the number of accessible or national .The scale of the work during the period of teaching Savod is extensive and is associated with excursions , observations of children, conversation on the subject and plot picture , and so on . The tasks of growing students ' speech during this period include:

1. Correcting deficiencies in students ' speech.
2. Enrich their vocabulary in connection with the expansion of the scope of their understanding and imagination;
3. Clarification of the meaning of certain words in the speech of readers;
4. Like cultivating the skill of verbally correct construction of a Gap and a small three-four-sentence story ...

The main resource for growing children's speech is children's personal experiences, people's life and nature observations. When growing the speech of teachers of the first grade, children's play and Ermak, to see a picture and say "what is it?, Who is it?, What is he doing?", a question-based conversation is also used.Special attention should be paid to the work of growing speech in each course of the lesson during the period of teaching .Particular attention should be paid to the fact that students can correctly apply one sound in speech when they learn it , not pronounce another in the place of one sound (for example , s in the place of sh), and not drop sounds in words.. It requires extreme caution when criticizing speech deficiencies found in elementary school students . A rude reproach given to them ,improper criticism can distort good treatment between students , offend students , therefore , it is necessary for the teacher to comply with the requirements of

pedagogical etiquette in colloquial treatment, strive to preserve the human dignity, reputation of students . In the process of studying the subject of mother tongue in general secondary educational institutions, the following competencies are formed in the student:

- speech compensation aimed at making the reader think privately ,realize the opinion of others, be able to make a literate statement of his personal opinion in oral and written form;

- linguistic competence aimed at the formation and development of knowledge about grammar in students and the formation of skills to be able to correctly and fluently state one's opinion, making the most of the wide possibilities of the native language.

During classes, the teacher should use the following recommendations to cultivate the students ' speech thinking, to form a speech culture:

1. During each lesson, the teacher uses a variety of methodological forms and methods aimed at growing the student's speech;
2. Working with exercises aimed at growing more oral speech with students;
3. When working with exercises aimed at growing oral speech, it should produce more monological and diological speech skills:

In addition , readers will be of great help when growing their speech , not only using techniques such as memorizing, explaining or retelling the meaning of words, but also using games that are interesting to them. Because the game occupies a key place in the activities of students of a small school age.Based on the age and psychological aspect of children, play is the main tool in understanding the world and the self , in the cultivation of connected speech. We bring examples of games that are used during classes:

"The fifth is superfluous."game

This game is played without pictures. A student or child is part of a group four objects and one object belonging to another group are named.

For example: rose, chamomile, purple, tulip, mushroom. After the reader says more than one of them, he should be asked to base his opinion. These games help the development of students' thinking, as well as contribute to the growth of their speech. The game works well even if it is played individually, the interest of students is further increased if the group is played in the form of a competition.

"Opposite words." game

This game contributes to the development of logical thinking and speech gives. The game can be played both individually and with a group. Game the condition is as follows: the teacher says a word to the child or student, the student is

must find and say a word that contrasts with the meaning of the word. For example: like big - small, dark - light, low - high.

Teacher speech plays a key role in the formation of speech skills in students. The teacher should pay special attention to the quality of students not only in the mother tongue lesson, but also in other lessons. The teacher should observe how his speech affects children, take into account what is understandable and interesting. If children sit unnoticed in the lesson, then the power of influence of the teacher's speech is weak. The teacher's skill is that he should not only educate the entire community with his pleasant speech, but also encourage them to strive for heights. The role of native language lessons is of great importance in the correct formation of speech of Primary School students. We can cite the following points of the Russian classical educator about this:

K.D. Ushinsky paid special attention to his native language in the system of elementary school educational subjects, considering it a central and leading subject. "The mother tongue, who is an excellent teacher, teaches the child a lot. .. The child learns so much in two three years that he learns so much that even when 20 years of diligent methodically study very correctly, he cannot learn about half of it. Such is the great pedagogy of the native language".

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